

Efficiency and Effectiveness of Implementation of Hydropower Development Policy in Nepal

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Abstract

It is evident that the hydro-power sector operates under a policy framework, where the success or failure of power development depends on favorable policy implementation. Nepal has struggled to fully leverage its hydro potential, with only a small fraction of its capacity exploited over the past century. Therefore, this study seeks to analyze the efficiency, effectiveness, and feasibility of Nepal's existing Hydropower Development Policy (HDP) of 2001. Judgmental sampling techniques were used due to the difficulty in determining the entire population and unit of analysis. Four independent variables like Financial Incentives Sufficiency (FIS), Return on Investment Sufficiency (RoIS), Market Access Sufficiency (MAS), and Legal Framework Sufficiency (LFS) along with a single dependent variable, Investment Friendliness (IF), were examined to gauge the perceptions of stakeholders using a five-point Likert scale. Frequency distribution, percentage along with statistical tools such as mean and standard deviation were employed. The empirical findings suggest that the HDP, 2001 generally meets investor expectations, indicating significant efficiency and effectiveness in policy implementation. Respondents expressed concerns regarding aspects such as mechanisms for wheeling charges, inadequate participation from the private sector, and delays in policy amendments. Moreover, substantial obstacles were emphasized in procedures related to land acquisition, environmental evaluations, and policy execution, underscoring the need for prompt revisions to accommodate evolving socio-economic and environmental factors.

Keywords: Hydropower Development Policy, Investment Friendliness, Policy Constraints, Nepal, Hydroelectricity Potentiality.

INTRODUCTION

Nepal's hydroelectric potential is globally recognized (ADB, 2020). It is estimated as 83,000 MW (Shrestha, H.M., 1966), with 42,143 MW deemed feasible (WECS, 2019). Despite this immense possibility, Nepal has only achieved a fraction of its potential, reaching 2,900 MW in installed capacity and a per capita electricity consumption of 365 KWh by March 2024 (NEA). Nepal's failure to capitalize on its hydroelectric potential is evident, as seen in its significant electricity imports and minimal exports (ERC, 2021).

Hydropower offers various benefits, including energy security, environmental preservation, and industrial development. However, numerous challenges hinder its promotion and development, including surveying, construction, distribution, subsidy allocation, land acquisition, and local demands. The current hydropower development policy, enacted in 2001, is outdated and inadequate to address contemporary challenges (Pradhan et al., 2018).

Past government plans for hydropower development have fallen short, with unrealized targets such as the 10,000 MW goal within ten years and the 25,000 MW target within twenty years (MoE, 2009; MoE, 2010). Despite this, the government now aims to generate 15,000 MW by 2029, with ongoing issues of electricity surplus and market uncertainty (NEA, 2022).

Critics argue that there's a lack of appropriate policies to encourage domestic resource utilization (WECS, 2013), and unresolved issues such as resettlement and rehabilitation plague mega projects like Budhigandaki, West-Seti, and Upper Karnali (Dhungana, 2019). Additionally, the absence of clear provisions for private sector involvement in electricity trade and market assurance further complicates matters (Pradhan et al., 2018).

Panth (2017) suggests that relaxing laws, rules, and regulations could expedite growth in this sector. Thapa (2016) highlights significant deficiencies in policies, leading to reluctance among private sector and international investors. MoE (2009) notes a lack of policy adaptability to evolving circumstances. Moreover, there is a noted absence of effective policies to stimulate domestic hydroelectric development (WECS, 2013). Nepal has not been able to fully utilize such potentialities. Given the focus on hydropower policy, this study was designed with the following objectives.

- a) To assess the efficiency, effectiveness, and feasibility of implementing the Hydropower Development Policy (HDP) of 2001 for strengthening the power sector.
- b) To identify the policy constraints and obstacles encountered by developers.
- c) To uncover new insights aimed at formulating a hydropower development policy conducive to investment.

METHOD

In this study, Financial Incentives Sufficiency (FIS), Return on Investment Sufficiency (RoIS), Market Access Sufficiency (MAS), and Legal Framework Sufficiency (LFS) were taken as

independent variables. Financial Incentives Sufficiency (FIS) encompasses factors such as rehabilitation and resettlement costs, tax burdens, fees, and royalty rates. In the same way Return on Investment Sufficiency (RoIS) includes elements like power purchase agreements, force majeure provisions, and security costs. Market Access Sufficiency (MAS) encompasses considerations such as the adequacy of the electricity market, trade freedom, and project duration. Similarly, Legal Framework Sufficiency (LFS) comprises aspects such as Nepal's Constitution of 2015, hydropower-related policies, acts, laws, regulations, and power-related treaties and agreements. On the other hand, Investment Friendly (IF) is considered as the dependent variable.

This study employed a mixed research design, primarily focusing on gathering primary data. The primary data was obtained through an online survey questionnaire developed on the KoboToolbox data collection platform. A total of 108 participants from 25 different sectors within the hydropower industry were selected using judgmental sampling techniques. These sectors include various government ministries such as the Ministry of Energy, Water Resources and Irrigation, Ministry of Forest and Environment, Ministry of Land Management, Cooperatives, and Poverty Alleviation, as well as entities like the Nepal Electricity Authority, investment board, experts, journalists, and representatives from foreign direct investments, among others.

The questionnaire comprised 33 questions, and data collection took place between October and December 2023. A five-point Likert scale was used to gauge respondents' perceptions of the Hydropower Development Policy of 2001. Quantitative data analysis was employed through frequency table, percentage, mean, standard deviation (Pradhan, 2017).

RESULT AND ANALYSIS

A total of 108 participants from diverse sectors who were involved in the hydropower industry, were surveyed using a 33 questions questionnaire. The responses were analyzed along with demographic information. The table 1 demonstrates the designation, level, work experience and category of information.

Table 1

Demographic characteristics of informants

Designation of Informants	Number of informants
CEO, MD, DMD, Directors, and Managers	37
Senior divisional and engineers and engineers (hydrology)	22
Secretary, former secretary, joint secretary, and under Secretary	12
Chairman, board member, and vice President	8
Editor and freelance	3
Practicing chartered accountants, financial consultants and Consultants	3
Advocate, policy analysis & professors	3

Environment expert & transmission expert	2
Level of informants	Number of informants
Executive level	21
Gazette first class	12
Gazette second class	12
Board member, advisory and regulatory	8
Gazette third class	3
Gazette special class	1
Work Experience of Informants (Years)	Number of informants
0 to 10	25
10 to 20	28
20 to 30	26
30 to 40	6
Category of Informants	Number of Informants
Government Sector (Policy formulator or Executer)	57
Private sector (IPPs or promoters)	43

The above table 1 shows the demographic information of the respondent. The information was optional so the total sum is not the same for each case. The informants in this study were from diverse sectors of the hydropower industry, held various designations, predominantly occupying positions in top management or involved in policy formulation and execution. Specifically, 37 informants were chief executive officers, managing directors, deputy managing directors, or managers; 22 were senior divisional engineers or engineers; 12 were secretaries, former secretaries, joint secretaries, or under secretaries; and 8 were chairpersons, board members, or vice presidents, with the remaining informants holding positions such as editor, freelance, practicing chartered accountant, financial consultant, consultant, advocate, policy analyst, professor, environment expert, or transmission expert.

These informants, primarily at administrative levels, had considerable work experience in the hydropower sector, with 53.54% having 10 to 35 years of experience, distributed among various sectors and levels within the industry. Additionally, the informants represented a balanced mix of government and private sector professionals, with 57% from the government sector and 43% from the private sector, ensuring inclusivity and enhancing the reliability of the study's information sources.

Efficiency and effectiveness of the Hydropower Development Policy, 2001

To measure the efficiency and effectiveness of the Hydropower Development Policy (HDP), 2001, ten major parameters of the policy were identified. These parameters encompass various aspects such as electric market sufficiency, power purchase agreement (PPA) rates, freedom in electric trade, project term durations, rehabilitation and resettlement costs, force majeure provisions, security costs, tax burdens, fee burdens, and rates of royalty.

The table below presents the perceptions of stakeholders on these major parameters, as quantified through a survey methodology, providing insight into the stakeholders' perspectives and facilitating a comprehensive assessment of the policy's efficacy and impact.

Table 1

Perception on Major Parameters of HDP, 2001

Opinion on	SD*	A**	N***	D****	SA*****	Mean	SD
Electric Market sufficiency	7(6.73)	37(35.57)	13(12.5)	36(34.61)	11(10.57)	58.38	20.82
PPA /Rate	7(6.93)	52(51.48)	18(17.82)	22(21.78)	2(1.98)	63.49	18.03
Electric trade Freedom	3(2.88)	42(40.38)	15(14.42)	13(12.5)	31(29.80)	63.80	26.27
Term of Project	5(5)	44(44)	21(21)	19(19)	11(11)	65.20	24.14
Rehabilitate and Resettle Cost	2(2)	47(47)	28(28)	20(20)	3(3)	59.76	17.48
Force Majeure	0(0)	63(61.16)	16(15.53)	14(13.59)	10(9.70)	65.92	20.10
Security Cost	6(5.769)	45(43.26)	26(25.00)	24(23.07)	3(2.88)	57.08	21.46
Tax Burden	6(5.76)	57(54.80)	13(12.50)	19(18.26)	9(8.65)	61.68	23.06
Fee Burden	1(0.96)	53(50.96)	23(22.12)	16(15.38)	11(10.57)	63.93	20.58
Rate of Royalty	1(0.97)	65(63.10)	16(15.53)	13(12.62)	8(7.76)	65.12	18.69

*SD*Strongly Disagree, A** Agree, N***Neutral, D**** Disagree, SA***** Strongly Agree*

Opinions on Electric Market Sufficiency show that out of 104 informants, 37 agreed, 36 disagreed, 13 remained neutral, 11 strongly agreed, and 7 strongly disagreed. The mean score for market sufficiency was 58.38, with a standard deviation of 20.82, indicating overall agreement that the electric market is sufficient.

Regarding Power Purchase Agreement, 52 informants agreed, 22 disagreed, 18 remained neutral, 7 strongly disagreed, and 2 strongly agreed, resulting in a mean score of 63.49 and a standard deviation of 18.04, suggesting that the rate of PPA is acceptable.

For Electricity Trade Freedom, 42 informants agreed, 31 strongly agreed, 15 remained neutral, 13 disagreed, and 3 strongly disagreed. The mean score was 63.80, with a standard deviation of 26.27, indicating a consensus on the importance of trade freedom in the electric industry.

Similarly, opinions on the Term of Project revealed that 44 informants agreed, with a mean score of 65.20 and a standard deviation of 24.14, indicating reliability in project duration.

Regarding Rehabilitate and Resettle provision, 47 informants agreed, resulting in a mean score of 59.76 and a standard deviation of 17.48, suggesting an acceptable level of cost incurred by developers.

On the question of Force Majeure, 63 informants agreed, with a mean score of 65.92 and a standard deviation of 20.10, indicating justifiability of the provision.

Security Concerns were deemed less congenial, with 45 informants agreeing and a mean score of 57.08 and a standard deviation of 21.46.

Tax Burden was considered bearable by 57 informants, resulting in a mean score of 61.68 and a standard deviation of 23.06.

Fee Burden was deemed allowable by 53 informants, with a mean score of 63.93 and a standard deviation of 20.58.

Lastly, the Rate of Royalty was considered tolerable by 65 informants, resulting in a mean score of 65.12 and a standard deviation of 18.69.

Complication of Transmission Network

The complication of the Transmission Network lies in its essential role of carrying electricity from powerhouses to end users, without which projects incur losses. Policy propositions to expedite transmission network completion include resolving Right of Way issues, amending the Land Acquisition Act of 2034, and making the Rastriya Prasaran Grid Company Ltd's performance result-oriented. Private sector participation, addressing delays due to governmental mechanisms, and reimbursing developers for losses due to incomplete transmission lines and sufficient budget allocation were also recommended.

Table 2

Policy Proposition to Compete Transmission Networks on Time

S.N.	Description	Frq.	%
1	Problem of "Right of way" should be resolved.	71	79.77
2	Land acquisition act, 2034 should be amended.	60	67.41
3	The performance of Rastriya Prasaran Grid Company Ltd should be made result-oriented.	50	56.17
4	Participation of the Private sector should be given.	48	53.93
5	Delay due to government mechanisms so, penalties should be made to responsible authorities.	45	50.56
6	Reimbursement should be given to those developers who incur loss due to non-complementation of transmission line.	44	49.43
7	Sufficient budget should be allocated.	42	47.19

89 out of 108 informants responded to this. Almost eighty percent of informants expressed their view on problem of right of way should be resolved, 67.41 percent were showing their agreement on land acquisition act, 2034 should be amendment and 56.17 percent on the respondent has expressed their view on the performance of Rastriya Prasaran Grid Company Ltd should be made result-oriented. However, only 47.19% of respondents agreed on allocating

a sufficient budget. Additional suggestions include making NEA more accountable, providing reimbursement to grid owners, avoiding unnecessary donor conditions, implementing NEA unbundling, formulating rehabilitation and resettlement policies promptly, streamlining tree felling and land acquisition procedures, reconciling conflicting policies, and enhancing public awareness on the importance of transmission networks.

Issue of Rehabilitation and Resettlement

The Issue of Rehabilitation and Resettlement in hydropower development involves the displacement and rehabilitation of households residing in areas where infrastructure for powerhouses, tunnels, dams, and transmission lines are to be constructed. This process is both challenging and costly. Problems faced by developers during this phase include demands for unfair compensation, a lack of investment-friendly policies for land acquisition and resettlement, reluctance to relocate, inadequate government assistance, and scarcity of land for resettlement.

Table 3: Problems Facing by Developers during Resettlement and Rehabilitation

S.N.	Description	Frq.	%
1	Demanding an unfair amount for displaced people.	75	78.12
2	Lack of investment friendly land acquisition, resettlement and rehabilitation policy.	60	62.50
3	Not being ready to resettle in the next place.	47	48.95
4	Lack of appropriate assistance by the government.	46	47.91
5	Most costly and most difficult job for hydro developers.	45	46.87
6	Lack of land to resettle.	42	43.75

Among the respondents, 78.12% highlighted the issue of demanding unfair compensation as the most significant problem, while 43.75% cited a lack of land for resettlement as the least significant issue. Other concerns included the absence of investment-friendly policies (62.50%), reluctance to relocate (48.95%), and inadequate government assistance (47.91%).

Issue of IEE/EIA

In addressing the complexities of hydropower project development, various societal, environmental, and public concerns must be navigated, including issues pertaining to forests, water bodies, and wildlife. To address these challenges, developers are required to conduct initial environmental examinations (IEE) or environmental impact assessments (EIA). However, this process is often fraught with difficulties and complexities.

Table 4 below outlines policy measures aimed at resolving issues related to IEE/EIA processes, reflecting stakeholder perceptions and suggesting potential solutions to streamline these procedures for more efficient and effective project development.

Table 4

Policy Measures to Resolve IEE/EIA Related Problems

S.N.	Description	Frq.	%
1	Procedure of EIA should be simplified, if IEE/EIA procedure is made complicated projects can't be developed .	73	73.73
2	IEE/EIA should be performed through skilled manpower/ should not copy and paste.	67	67.67
3	Project capacity up to 100 MW should be put into the arena of IEE instead of 50MW.	35	35.35
4	Scope of IEE should extend from 50MW to 100MW in order to motivate developers.	34	34.34
5	The EIA report should be ratified by the Ministry of forest and environment instead of the cabinet.	28	28.28

The most supported measures include simplifying the EIA procedure to avoid hindering project development, ensuring that IEE/EIA processes are conducted by skilled personnel without resorting to copying, and extending the scope of IEE/EIA to cover projects up to 100MW. Other suggestions include ratifying EIA reports by the Ministry of Forest and Environment instead of the cabinet and motivating developers by expanding the scope of IEE to cover projects up to 100MW.

In addition, further recommendations have been proposed to streamline the procedures of Initial Environmental Examination (IEE) and Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA). These suggestions focus on reducing procedural complexities, implementing effective monitoring mechanisms, improving inter-agency coordination, ensuring the quality of reports, adopting river basin-based cumulative assessments, and establishing a centralized mechanism based on a one-door policy. Consequently, many hydro-promoters perceive the IEE/EIA process as burdensome. Adhakari (2017), emphasizes the necessity of minimizing procedural complexities associated with IEE/EIA, advocating for simplification whenever feasible.

Issue of Land Acquisition

The acquisition of land for hydropower projects, involving essential components such as powerhouse, tunnels, dams, and transmission lines, is known to be a challenging and resource intensive endeavor, as noted by Pandit(2019). Local communities residing in the area adjacent to these projects are particularly susceptible to their impacts, with issues such as land acquisition and displacement of residents being of significant concern. The Table 5

below highlights the key challenges faced by developers in acquiring land for hydropower projects.

Table 5

Problems Facing by Developers to have Acquire Land

S.N.	Description	Frq.	%
1	Procedure of acquiring excess land than the upper ceiling is overly lengthy and painful.	67	69.07
2	Upper ceiling i.e. 70 Ropani land in mountainous region is insufficient.	62	63.91
3	Land acquired excess than the upper ceiling cannot be sold.	55	56.70
4	Such excess land cannot be used to get a loan from a bank .	45	46.39

Ninety seven respondents responded to this question. Key issues include the lengthy and cumbersome procedures for acquiring land exceeding specified limits, the inadequacy of upper ceiling limits, restrictions on selling excess land acquired, and limitations on using excess land as collateral for bank loans. These findings underscore the significant hurdles and complexities involved in land acquisition for hydropower development.

Policy Measures for Land Acquisition

Addressing the complexities of land acquisition in hydropower project development often requires the implementation of well-defined policies. These policies play a crucial role in ensuring fairness, legality, and financial feasibility throughout the acquisition process. The subsequent table presents policy measures proposed by stakeholders to tackle land acquisition challenges, aiming to establish transparent compensation mechanisms, clarify legal ambiguities, and enhance accessibility to financial resources.

Table 6

Policy Measure Addressing the Problems of Land Acquisition

S.N.	Description	Frq.	%
1	Compensation amount of land must be justifiable.	80	81.63
2	Limitation of land acquisition should be legally resolved.	61	62.24
3	Land could be received at the price determined by the government.	51	52.04
4	Land acquired excessively above the upper ceiling could be used in order to get a loan from the bank .	43	43.87
5	policy should be initiated for banks to accept the lands under transmission line on mortgage.	41	41.83

The table illustrates stakeholders' recommendations for policy interventions addressing land acquisition issues. A significant majority of respondents advocate for justifiable compensation,

while others emphasize legal clarity, government-set land prices, and facilitating bank loans against excess land. These findings underscore the importance of equitable policies in navigating the complexities of land acquisition for hydropower projects.

Additional recommendations have been put forth, including setting standardized categories and rates for land, removing the maximum limit on land acquisition for hydropower projects, permitting developers to sell acquired land for any use, simplifying procedures for acquiring forest land, addressing compensation for lands with unclear ownership, and granting approval for subdividing plots located within transmission corridors.

Lapses in Existing Hydropower Development policy, 2001

It has been 22 years since the promulgation of the Hydropower Development Policy (HDP), 2001. However, the implementation of this policy has faced various challenges over time. Legislative changes and evolving industry dynamics have highlighted several shortcomings in the existing policy framework. Some stakeholders argue that there are significant lapses that require attention, such as the absence of provisions for private sector participation in electricity trade and the need for an extension of project terms to 50 years. Table 7 illustrates the identified lapses in the Hydropower Development Policy, 2001, as reported by stakeholders.

Table 7

Lapses on Hydropower Development policy, 2001

S.N.	Description	Frq.	%
1	Lack of Wheeling charge arrangement.	66	68.75
2	Lack of hedging fund related mechanism.	64	66.66
3	Lack of participation of the private sector in electric trade.	60	62.50
4	Lack of timely amendment of existing hydropower policy, 2001.	59	61.45
5	Lack of Perfectly implementation existing hydro policy, 2001.	55	57.29
6	Lack of mechanism of operation of hydro projects after completion of the project term.	36	37.50
7	Founding shareholder's share and period of investment to be continued.	33	34.37

Among the seven listed issues, the most prevalent concern is the lack of a wheeling charge arrangement, highlighted by 68.75% of respondents. This is followed closely by the absence of a hedging fund-related mechanism, with 66.66% of respondents indicating this as a significant issue. Other notable concerns include the lack of private sector participation in electric trade (62.50%), the need for timely amendments to the existing policy (61.45%), and challenges in implementing the existing policy effectively (57.29%).

The survey was conducted among 108 informants, with 96 providing responses to the checklist of issues related to the lapses in the HDP, 2001.

CONCLUSION

The study delved into various facets of Nepal's hydropower development policy (HDP) to assess its efficacy and identify areas for improvement. The examined constructs included the sufficiency of the electric market, the reliability of power purchasing agreements, the freedom of electric trade, the duration of project terms, the costs associated with rehabilitation and resettlement, provisions for force majeure and license extensions, security costs, tax and fee burdens, royalty rates, and the availability of hedging mechanisms.

While the overall perception of the HDP, 2001 was deemed favorable based on the combined mean score of 62.436, individual constructs revealed varying degrees of agreement among stakeholders. For instance, while stakeholders generally agreed on the reliability of power purchasing agreements and the sufficiency of the electric market, concerns were raised regarding issues such as the lack of a mechanism for wheeling charges and hedging funds, insufficient private sector participation in electric trade, and delays in policy amendments.

Furthermore, the study highlighted significant challenges in areas such as land acquisition procedures, environmental impact assessments, and the implementation of policies. These challenges underscored the need for timely policy revisions to address evolving socio-economic and environmental dynamics and ensure the sustainability of hydropower projects. Moreover, the study emphasized the importance of conducting comprehensive and scientific research to bridge existing gaps in understanding and inform evidence-based policy decisions.

In conclusion, while the HDP, 2001 was generally perceived as investment-friendly, addressing the identified challenges and revising policies in line with current realities are essential to facilitate sustainable hydropower development in Nepal and harness its potential as a renewable energy source.

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